

Appendix B: Observations

Date	Program ID	Spectrum	Wavelength (Å)	Start time (UT)	Exposure time (s)	Grating	RV ranges showing comet absorption (km/s)
1997-12-06	7512	o4g001010	1463 - 1661	07:18'	900	E140H	[-4;+200]
		o4g001030	1628 - 1902	07:48'	679	E230H	
		o4g001020	1879 - 2150	07:42'	80	E230H	
		o4g001060	2128 - 2396	09:16'	288	E230H	
		o4g001050	2377 - 2650	09:02'	360	E230H	
		o4g001040	2620 - 2888	08:48'	360	E230H	
1997-12-19	7512	o4g002010	1463 - 1661	19:51'	900	E140H	[-17;+19], [+50;+150]
		o4g002030	1628 - 1902	20:22'	679	E230H	
		o4g002020	1879 - 2150	20:14'	80	E230H	
		o4g002060	2128 - 2396	21:53'	288	E230H	
		o4g002050	2377 - 2650	21:40'	360	E230H	
		o4g002040	2620 - 2888	21:26'	360	E230H	
2001-08-26	9154	o6fp01010	1499 - 1687	05:59'	400	E140H	[-17;-3]
		o6fp01040	1499 - 1687	08:52'	400	E140H	
2001-08-27	9154	o6fp02010	1628 - 1897	01:15'	210	E230H	[-17;-3]
2002-05-21	9154	o6fp03010	1834 - 2103	17:03'	200	E230H	[]
2002-05-22	9154	o6fp04010	2327 - 2606	17:09'	200	E230H	[-8,40]
2017-10-09	14735	odaa01010	2665 - 2931	23:40'	475	E230H	[-35;+120]
2018-01-10	14735	odaa03010	2665 - 2931	08:12'	475	E230H	[-70;0], [+19;+150]
2018-03-07	14735	odaa62010	2665 - 2931	02:33'	475	E230H	[-40;+13]
2018-10-29	15479	odt901010	2665 - 2931	21:49'	2101	E230H	[-30;-4], [+8;+140]
2018-12-15	15479	odt902010	2665 - 2931	04:22'	2101	E230H	[-40;+50]

Table B.1. Log of HST/STIS observations used in the present study.

Appendix C: Comparison between Fe II, Ni II and Mn II lines

Fig. C.1. Zoomed-in view of a few Fe II, Ni II and Mn II lines in β Pic spectrum, at two different epochs (December 6 and 19, 1997). The grey area indicates the RV range (21-42 km/s) used to measure the December 6, 1997 comet's absorption depth throughout the study. For each epoch, all lines were observed within the same HST orbit, and are thus very close in time. The comet's absorption profile appears to be very similar from one species to another (same radial velocity, same width), although it seems slightly sharper in Fe II and Ni II than in Mn II.

Fig. C.2. Same as Fig. C.1 for Fe II, Ni II and Si II lines. Again, the six lines were observed during the same HST orbit, for both visits.

Fig. C.3. Same as Fig. C.1 for Cr II lines, emphasising the December 6, 1997 observation (purple line). Contrary to Figs. C.1 and C.2, the December 6, 1997 spectrum is compared to our reconstructed exocomet-free spectrum (EFS, black line), the December 19 observation being too noisy to allow a visual comparison.

Appendix D: List of the studied lines

Table D.1. List of the Fe II lines used in this study, sorted by lower level energy. The notations are the same as in Sect. 3. The three lowest terms are studied in Sect. 3 ($E_l = 0\text{--}8847\text{ cm}^{-1}$), while more excited levels are included in Sect. 5 ($E_l = 15845\text{--}32910\text{ cm}^{-1}$).

Configuration	Term	J	E_l^a (cm^{-1})	E_l/k_B (K)	λ_{lu}^a ($\text{\AA}$)	A_{ul}^a (10^7 s^{-1})	$g_l f_{lu}^a$		
3d ⁶ (⁵ D)4s	a ⁶ D	9/2	0	0	2249.88	0.30	0.018		
					2260.78	0.32	0.024		
					2374.46	4.25	0.36		
					2382.76	31.3	3.20		
					2586.65	8.94	0.72		
					2600.17	23.5	2.38		
		7/2	385	554	2253.82	0.44	0.027		
					2280.62	0.45	0.035		
					2333.51	13.1	0.64		
					2365.55	5.90	0.40		
					2389.36	10.5	0.72		
					2396.35	25.9	2.23		
					2612.65	12.0	0.98		
					2626.45	3.57	0.36		
	5/2	668	961	2251.63	0.32	0.015			
				2268.29	0.37	0.023			
				2328.11	6.60	0.21			
				2349.02	11.5	0.57			
				2381.49	3.10	0.21			
				2399.97	13.9	0.72			
				2405.62	19.6	1.36			
				2607.87	17.3	0.71			
				2618.40	4.88	0.30			
				2632.11	6.29	0.52			
				3/2	863	1241	2261.56	0.22	0.010
							2338.73	11.3	0.37
							2359.83	5.00	0.25
							2407.39	16.1	0.56
2614.60	21.2	0.44							
2614.60	21.2	0.44							
1/2	977	1406	2345.00	9.27	0.31				
			2411.80	23.7	0.41				
			2414.04	10.2	0.36				
			2622.45	5.60	0.115				
			2629.08	8.74	0.36				
			2629.08	8.74	0.36				
3d ⁷	a ⁴ F	9/2	1873	2694	2332.02	3.17	0.21		
					2361.02	6.20	0.31		
					2362.74	1.41	0.094		
					2380.00	2.73	0.185		
		7/2	2430	3497	2392.21	0.38	0.032		
					2392.21	0.38	0.032		
					2392.21	0.38	0.032		
					2392.21	0.38	0.032		
	5/2	2838	4083	2355.61	2.67	0.089			
				2367.32	1.01	0.051			
				2369.32	6.10	0.204			
				2385.73	0.36	0.025			
	3/2	3117	4485	2371.22	1.73	0.058			
				2375.92	9.80	0.166			
				2385.11	3.20	0.109			
				2385.11	3.20	0.109			

^a The level energies and line parameters (λ_{lu} , A_{ul} , f_{lu}) were all collected from the NIST database (Kramida et al. 2023). The uncertainties are typically of the order of 10 %.

Table D.1, continued.

Configuration	Term	J	E_l (cm^{-1})	E_l/k_B (K)	λ_{lu} ($\text{\AA}$)	A_{ul} (10^7 s^{-1})	$g_l f_{lu}$
3d ⁶ (⁵ D)4s	a ⁴ D	7/2	7955	11446	2563.30	17.9	1.06
					2715.22	5.70	0.38
					2740.36	22.1	1.99
					2756.55	21.5	2.45
	5/2	8392	12074	2564.27	1.73	0.058	
				2592.31	5.70	0.35	
				2725.69	0.96	0.064	
				2728.35	9.38	0.42	
				2747.79	16.9	1.15	
	3/2	8680	12490	2567.68	11.0	0.22	
				2583.36	8.80	0.35	
				2731.54	2.79	0.125	
				2737.78	12.2	0.27	
				2769.75	0.48	0.033	
	1/2	8847	12729	2578.69	12.0	0.24	
				2744.01	19.7	0.89	
2762.66				1.38	0.063		
3d ⁷	a ² G	9/2	15845	22797	1746.82	12.1	0.55
		7/2	16369	23553	1761.37	14.2	0.53
3d ⁶ (³ P2)4s	b ⁴ P	5/2	20831	29971	2445.26	27.8	1.99
					2527.05	24.7	1.42
		3/2	21812	31383	2446.31	20.7	1.11
3d ⁶ (³ H)4s	a ⁴ H	13/2	21251	30577	2526.15	19.1	2.56
		11/2	21430	30834	2534.39	19.2	2.22
		9/2	21582	31052	2499.65	21.2	2.38
		7/2	21712	31239	2512.52	23.0	2.18
					2535.18	18.3	1.41
3d ⁶ (³ F2)4s	b ⁴ F	9/2	22637	32571	2424.88	22.1	2.34
					2480.91	15.5	1.14
					2530.31	22.0	2.11
		7/2	22810	32820	2430.82	19.1	1.69
					2471.42	15.4	0.85
3d ⁵ 4s ²	a ⁶ S	5/2	23317	33550	1785.28	109	4.17
					1786.76	110	3.16
3d ⁶ (³ G)4s	a ⁴ G	11/2	25429	36587	2440.04	22.5	2.81
					2490.58	19.4	2.17
					2459.53	23.1	2.51
	9/2	25805	37129	2459.53	23.1	2.51	
				2459.53	23.1	2.51	
7/2	25982	37383	2462.60	24.3	2.21		

^a The 2530.31 $\text{\AA}$ line is blended with another Fe II transition at 2530.32 $\text{\AA}$ ($E_l = 21812 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $gf = 0.78$). An effective gf -value of 2.89 was thus used for this line.

Table D.1. continued.

Configuration	Term	J	E_l (cm^{-1})	E_l/k_B (K)	λ_{lu} ($\text{\AA}$)	A_{ul} (10^7 s^{-1})	$g_l f_{lu}$	
3d ⁶ (³ H)4s	b ² H	11/2	26170	37654	2490.58	19.4	2.17	
					2768.32	15.8	2.55	
	9/2	26353	37917	2550.79	17.9	1.75		
				2754.10	18.9	2.58		
	3d ⁶ (³ G)4s	b ² G	9/2	30389	43723	2504.63	22.3	2.10
						2693.40	14.0	1.83
7/2		30764	44264	2515.14	21.1	1.60		
				2685.55	15.7	1.70		
d ⁶ (¹ D)4s	a ² I	13/2	32876	47302	2433.61	28.6	3.56	
					2593.56	27.4	4.42	
	11/2	32910	47351	2435.47	27.9	1.98		
				2448.50	19.7	1.77		

Table D.2. List of the Cr II lines used in this study, sorted by lower level energy.

Configuration	Term	J	E_l^a (cm^{-1})	E_l/k_B (K)	λ_{lu}^a ($\text{\AA}$)	A_{ul}^a (10^7 s^{-1})	$g_l f_{lu}^a$
3d ⁵	a ⁶ S	5/2	0	0	2056.26	1.22	0.62
					2062.24	1.19	0.46
					2066.16	1.20	0.31
3d ⁴ (⁵ D)4s	a ⁶ D	3/2	12033	17313	2669.50	10.0	0.85
					2679.59	8.02	0.52
					2856.51	11.3	0.83
					2867.58	13.6	0.67
	5/2	12148	17478	2672.60	10.9	0.47	
				2751.54	9.56	0.65	
				2850.67	15.2	1.48	
				2865.95	11.1	0.82	
	7/2	12304	17703	2673.62	5.74	0.37	
				2844.08	18.9	2.29	
				2863.41	8.66	0.85	
	9/2	12496	17980	2677.95 ^b	20.9	2.25	
				2767.35	22.3	2.05	
				2836.47	25.0	3.62	

^a The level energies of Cr II were obtained from the NIST database, as well as the line parameters for the ground level. For the lines rising from the a⁶D term, the NIST database appears to be very incomplete. We thus used the values from Nilsson et al. (2006).

^b The 2677.95 $\text{\AA}$ line is strongly blended with another Cr II line ($E_l = 12304 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $gf = 1.02$), with $\Delta RV \sim 200 \text{ m/s}$. A corrected gf -value of 3.28 was thus used for this doublet line.

Table D.3. List of the Ni II lines used in this study, sorted by lower level energy.

Configuration	Term	J	E_l^a (cm^{-1})	E_l/k_B (K)	λ_{lu}^a ($\text{\AA}$)	A_{ul}^a (10^7 s^{-1})	$g_l f_{lu}^a$			
3p ⁶ 3d ⁹	² D	5/2	0	0	1703.41	1.86	0.032			
					1709.61	7.25	0.191			
					1741.56	9.48	0.259			
					1751.92	4.55	0.168			
					1773.95	0.67	0.025			
		1804.47	0.71	0.028						
		3/2	1507	2168	1754.81	2.30	0.064			
					1788.49	3.50	0.101			

					3p ⁶ 3d ⁸ (³ F)4s	⁴ F	9/2	8394	12077	2166.23
2217.17	3.40									3.01
2223.64	9.80	0.73								
2316.75	2.88	1.85								

7/2	9330	13424	2169.77	15.8			0.89			
			2211.07	3.90			0.29			
			2225.55	16.5			0.98			
			2270.91	15.6			1.21			
			2303.70	29.0			1.38			
5/2	10116	14555	2175.82	17.7	0.75					
			2207.41	16.6	0.97					
			2227.02	13.0	0.58					
			2265.16	14.3	0.88					

3p ⁶ 3d ⁸ (³ F)4s	² F	7/2	13550	19496	2279.47	28.0	1.31			
					2297.26	19.8	1.25			
					2395.25	17.0	1.46			
					2438.63	5.40	0.48			
					2511.63	5.80	0.55			
		5/2	14996	21576	2287.79	28.0	0.88			
					2298.98	28.0	1.33			
					2416.87	21.0	1.47			
					2546.66	1.56	0.12			

^a The level energies of Ni II were obtained from the NIST database. For the line parameters (λ_{lu} , λ_{lu} , f_{lu}), we used the values from Boissé & Bergeron (2019) for the ground state, Fedchak & Lawler (1999) for the 1507 cm^{-1} state, and the NIST database for higher levels.

Appendix E: Energy distribution of Fe⁺ under various physical conditions

Fig. E.1. Results from our Fe⁺ excitation model in the radiative regime (Sect. 5.3.1), for $n_e = 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $T_e = 50\,000 \text{ K}$, $d = 20 R_\star$. **Top:** Calculated relative abundances for all 340 Fe II levels. The two branches are clearly visible: the less excited branch corresponds to low excitation energies ($\leq 80\,000 \text{ K}$) and high abundances ($\frac{N_i}{g_i N_{\text{tot}}} \sim 10^{-6}$ to 10^{-2}), while the excited branch is characterised by high energies ($\geq 55\,000 \text{ K}$) and strong depletion ($\frac{N_i}{g_i N_{\text{tot}}} \leq 10^{-8}$). Here, the effect of collisions is negligible, due to the low electronic density. The calculated energy distribution is thus not impacted by the electronic temperature. **Bottom:** Comparison between calculated abundances and measurements from various Fe⁺ excitation energy levels observed in the December 6, 1997 comet. In the radiative regime, we obtain a fairly good agreement between the theoretical results and the measurements. The peculiar $a^6S_{5/2}$ level (33 550 K) is highlighted in turquoise colour.

Fig. E.2. Results from our Fe^+ excitation model in the semi-collisional regime (Sect. 5.3.2), for $n_e = 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $T_e = 50\,000 \text{ K}$, $d = 20 R_\star$. **Top:** Calculated relative abundances for all 340 Fe II levels. Due to electronic collisions, the excitation temperature for low-lying levels is increased in comparison to the lower density case with $n_e = 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (Fig. E.1). **Bottom:** Comparison between calculated abundances and measurements from various Fe^+ excitation energy levels observed in the December 6, 1997 comet. In this case, the outcome of the model is highly inconsistent with our measurements.

Fig. E.3. Results from our Fe^+ excitation model in the semi-collisional regime (Sect. 5.3.2), for $n_e = 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $T_e = 2000 \text{ K}$, $d = 20 R_\star$. **Top:** Calculated relative abundances for all 340 Fe II levels. Here, contrary to Fig. E.2, collisions with electrons tend to reduce the excitation temperature of the low-excitation branch, as the kinetic temperature (2000 K) is lower than the stellar effective temperature (8000 K). **Bottom:** Comparison between calculated abundances and measurements from various Fe^+ excitation energy levels observed in the December 6, 1997 comet. Similarly to Fig. E.2, the agreement between our calculations and the observed Fe II energy distribution is very poor.

Fig. E.4. Results from our Fe^+ excitation model in the semi-collisional regime (Sect. 5.3.2), for $n_e = 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $T_e = 8000 \text{ K}$, $d = 20 R_\star$. **Top:** Calculated relative abundances for all 340 Fe II levels. Here, the electronic temperature (8000 K) is equal to the stellar effective temperature, leading to a peculiar regime: both radiation and collision tend to populate Fe^+ at the same excitation temperature. The effect of collision is thus here barely noticeable, contrary to the previous semi-collisional examples (Fig. E.2 and E.3). **Bottom:** Comparison between calculated abundances and measurements from various Fe^+ excitation energy levels observed in the December 6, 1997 comet. In this peculiar case, we obtain a fairly good agreement between the theoretical results and the measurements.

Fig. E.5. Results from our Fe⁺ excitation model in the large distance regime (Sect. 5.3.3), for $n_e = 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $T_e = 50000 \text{ K}$, $d = 280 R_\star = 2 \text{ au}$. **Top:** Calculated abundances for all 340 Fe II levels. The result is somehow similar to the radiative regime (Fig. E.1), but here spontaneous emission in forbidden transitions start to play a significant role, depleting all excitation level to the benefit of the ground state. **Bottom:** Comparison between calculated abundances and measurements from the December 6, 1997 comet. The model agreement is poorer than in the radiative regime.

Appendix F: χ^2 maps for various comet-to-star distances

Fig. F.1. χ^2 maps calculated in Sect. 5.4, characterising the agreement between the observed Fe^+ excitation diagram in the December 6, 1997 comet, and the results from our excitation model. The six maps were calculated at different comet-to-star distances (d). The x-axis shows the electronic temperature within the comet (T_e), the y-axis shows its electronic density (n_e), and different colours indicate the χ^2 value for the corresponding parameters (n_e , T_e , d). The acceptable parameter space is shown with deep blue colour; the red line shows the $\chi^2_{\min} + 4$ contour, associated with a 95 % confidence. Letters indicate the different regimes compatible with our data (see Sect. 5.4): a radiative regime associated with a low electronic density (a), a semi-collisional regime at an electronic temperature close to 8000 K (b), and a large distance regime with $n_e \simeq 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $T_e \geq 10^4 \text{ K}$ (c).

Appendix G: View of the studied spectra

Fig. G.1. Extended view of the two β Pic spectra obtained in 1997 (December 6 and December 19). The Fe II, Ni II and Cr II lines used in the present study are indicated with solid lines and different colours. Dotted lines indicate lines not included in our study, associated with various species (Fe II, Fe I, Mn II...). The redshifted absorption of the December 6, 1997 comet is clearly visible in most of the spectral lines

Figure G.1, continued.

Figure G.1, continued.

Fig. G.2.

Figure G.1, continued.

Figure G.1, continued.

Figure G.1, continued.

Figure G.1, continued.

Figure G.1, continued.